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1. Executive Summary

The GUTTA project elaborated a Communication Strategy (CS) corresponding to its deliverable D.2.1.3. The CS envisions that printed materials support the progress of the project itself and externally disseminate implemented activities. The production of printed and electronic brochures with important facts about the project and its goals in Croatian, Italian and English language will contribute to this type of dissemination.

2. Introduction

Despite the great digitalisation of the media, printed brochures still have a quite powerful advertising, propaganda and informational potential on the majority of the population. They rely on specific design choices for conveying simple messages to either generic or targeted readers.

Design is a comprehensive concept that can be understood as embedding graphical and communication practices in the process of a product development, while paying attention to ethics and the socio-economic dimension.

The responsible partner for the design of the GUTTA brochures was UniZd, that operated in cooperation with the Communication Officer of the project (Laura Caciagli).

For reaching a broader target, the project brochures were realized in English, Croatian and Italian. The project brochure format is squared, with a side of 19 cm. Cohering with GUTTA project's commitment to environmental awareness, brochures are printed on recycled paper. The brochures outline in particular the three Specific Objectives (SO) of the GUTTA project. The distribution of brochures will occur during foreseen project events (SC meetings, conferences, project final events) as well as on demand.

3. Methodology

The brochures are printed on four pages, which are described in detail in the following.

Page 1

The page is structured into three horizontal bands.

The IT-HR graphical elements of the cyan wave, the Interreg logo, the GUTTA project bubble with the expanded GUTTA acronym "savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region", and the grey droplet with the Axis 4 "Maritime Transport" of the IT-HR Programme are displayed in the upper band.

The central band includes the payoff of the project "Towards a sustainable transportation in the Adriatic Sea" and a photo of a ferryboat sailing in rough sea.

The lower band includes the logos of the five GUTTA project partners.

Page 2

The page is structured into two horizontal bands.

The upper part contains text about the GUTTA specific and communication objectives.

The lower part contains three graphical elements with key project figures: its duration, its total budget, and the financial contribution provided from the European Union through the ERDF instrument.

Page 3

The page is organized into four quadrants.

Three of them includes a map of the Adriatic. In each map, one of the SO of GUTTA is presented in a visual form through icons and drawings. The icon for the ship routing (SO 1) is taken from a repository of open vector graphic on technologies, methods and policies that can help to mitigate climate change:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Climate_change_solutions_icons

In the fourth quadrant (lower left) the SO are listed in relation to the map number.

Page 4

The page is structured into two horizontal bands.

The upper one includes a broad-reach view of a ferryboat, this time sailing in a calm sea. This should convey a feeling of safety, relax and satisfaction, corresponding to the (hopefully) successful implementation of the project SO illustrated in the previous pages.

The lower part includes again the GUTTA/Interreg logo, a QR code pointing to the institutional project webpage <https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta> and the recyclable paper certification symbols. With recycled paper, we want to take care of the environment, and in this way, encourage the reader of the brochure to engage in recycling and waste management.

The company that realized the graphical layout and printing is Grafikart d.o.o. It has been operating for twenty years with relevant Institutions and successful companies in the Zadar County (Croatia).

4. Results

The brochures were printed in the following amounts:

- Italian language: 100 copies
- Croatian language: 100 copies
- English language: 150 copies

Their screenshots are reported in the following of this section.

Italian language

Page 1

Page 2

Il progetto

GUTTA mira a ridurre le emissioni di CO2 legate al trasporto marittimo nel mare Adriatico.

Il progetto si concentrerà sui traghetti e avrà tre obiettivi specifici:

- 1) Riduzione delle emissioni di CO2 mediante un'applicazione intelligente basata sulle previsioni meteorologiche
- 2) Supporto al processo di monitoraggio, reportistica, e verifica delle emissioni di CO2
- 3) Porre le basi per l'istituzione di una nuova rotta transfrontaliera tra Italia e Croazia

GUTTA stabilirà un canale di comunicazione con cittadini ed esperti del settore, determinando un cambiamento tangibile nella connettività transfrontaliera e nella coesione territoriale.

Page 3

Obiettivi Specifici di GUTTA

- ① Realizzare un sistema pilota per pianificare rotte di traghetti che minimizzino le emissioni di CO2
- ② Supportare il Regolamento EU-MRV 757/2015 sulle emissioni marittime di CO2
- ③ Facilitare l'istituzione di una nuova rotta transfrontaliera Italia-Croazia

Page 4

Croatian language

Page 1

Page 2

O projektu

GUTTA ima cilj smanjiti emisije plinova CO₂ s brodova u Jadranskom moru.

Projekt će se fokusirati na trajektnu liniju i imat će tri specifična cilja:

- 1) Smanjenje emisije CO₂ plinova upotrebom smart aplikacije temeljene na meteorološkim prognozama
- 2) Podrška procesu praćenja/izvještavanja/provjera emisija CO₂
- 3) Priprema podloge za novu prekograničnu rutu između Italije i Hrvatske

GUTTA će također uspostaviti komunikacijski kanal s građanima i stručnjacima što će rezultirati vidljivom promjenom u prekograničnoj povezanosti i teritorijalnoj koheziji.

Page 3

GUTTA specifični ciljevi

- ① Uvođenje pilot sustava za planiranje trajektnih ruta koje umanjuju emisije CO2 plinova
- ② Potpora EU MRV 757/2015 regulative o pomorskoj emisiji CO2
- ③ Uspostavljanje nove trajektno prekogranične rute između Italije i Hrvatske

Page 4

English language

Page 1

Page 2

The project

GUTTA aims to reduce CO2 emissions from maritime transport in the Adriatic Sea.

The project will focus on ferry lines and will have three specific objectives:

- 1) Reducing CO2 emissions by a smart application based on meteorological forecasts
- 2) Supporting the process of Monitoring-Reporting-Verifying of CO2 emissions
- 3) Preparing the ground for a new cross-border route between Italy and Croatia

GUTTA will also establish a communication channel with citizens and professionals, resulting in a visible change in cross-border connectivity and territorial cohesion.

Page 3

GUTTA Specific Objectives

- ① To realize a pilot-system for planning ferry routes that minimize the CO2 emissions
- ② To support the EU-MRV regulation 757/2015 on maritime CO2 emissions
- ③ To facilitate the establishment of a new Italy-Croatia cross-border route

Page 4

5. Conclusions

The creation of project brochures will contribute to the Communication Strategy of the GUTTA project. In particular, the target group “General Public” will be reached through them. Project brochures will be distributed at various events and meetings, providing essential information and key figures about the project itself. The visible impact will contribute to an immediate perception of the project and the reader will familiarize with its brand and key goals.

Last but not the least, we note that the paper used for printing the GUTTA brochures can be recycled up to five times.